

counts were made on 26 uncaged plants randomly selected in each field.

Except on the uncaged plants treated with carbofuran, the BPH populations on all plants examined were drastically reduced soon after treatment (see figure). That confirms earlier glasshouse findings that both chemicals were highly effective. Monocrotophos acted very rapidly, causing 100% BPH mortality 6 hours after treatment. But 3.6 BPH/hill were still alive on carbofuran-treated plants at 1 day after broadcasting. On plants of both cage treatments, however,

1st-instar nymphs emerged 2 days after treatment, suggesting that BPH eggs were already present and were not affected. Macropterous adults soon reappeared on exposed monocrotophos-treated plants and, like those on exposed carbofuran-treated plants, rapidly increased. The buildups were undoubtedly due to immigrants, as the populations consisted largely of macropterous adults from nearby fields of mature plants. Under such a situation, the fresh BPH influx not only nullifies the potential effectiveness of the applied insecticides but also leads to serious hopperburn (see table).

The findings revealed that 1) heavy immigration of BPH can render potentially effective chemicals ineffective, and 2) hopperburn will ensue when the reinfestation rate exceeds the rate of insecticidal kill, leaving a BPH population

Effectiveness of carbofuran and monocrotophos in the control of the brown planthoppers under outbreak condition in Sekinchan, Malaysia.

Plant conditions in a 2-ha rice field (variety MR 7) treated with 2 kg a.i. carbofuran/ha during a brown planthopper outbreak in Sekinchan, Malaysia, 1977.

Date	Plants (%)			
	Green	Slight yellowing	Intense yellowing	Hopperburn
<i>July 1977</i>				
20 ^a	100	0	—	—
21	95	5	—	—
22	95	5	—	—
23	90	10	—	—
26	75	25	—	—
28	70	30	—	—
29	60	40	—	—
30	40	30	30	—
<i>August 1977</i>				
1	15	40	40	5

^aBroadcast of carbofuran granules.

that exceeds the economic injury level. Those factors probably contribute to or account for the numerous unsuccessful

attempts to control large-scale BPH outbreaks by chemicals in many countries. ❧

Spray volumes in relation to brown planthopper control

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The Philippine recommendations for brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* control in rice state that 333, 500, and 1,000 liters water/ha are required to spray crops at 15, 35, and 60 days after transplanting (DT), respectively. It is extremely difficult for the applicator to carry this much water over 1 ha of lowland rice. An IRRI Cropping Systems Program survey indicated that most farmers apply only about 135 liters/ha.

Studies were conducted in 1977 to

determine the relationship between volume of spray solution applied and BPH control. Perthane was applied at 60 DT. The percentage of BPH control was equal for all volumes from 200 to

1,000 liters/ha (see table). Results in a repeated experiment were similar. Further studies with other insecticides will be conducted before current recommendations are reevaluated.

Effect of spray volumes on the control of the brown planthopper (BPH) on variety IR22. IRR1, 1977 wet season^a

Treatment 0.75 kg a.i. Perthane/ha at indicated volumes (liters)	Concn (%)	BPH ^b (no./hill)		Control (%)
		Before spraying	4 days after spraying	
200	0.38	911 a	112 a	88
400	0.19	750 a	98 a	87
600	0.13	867 a	66 a	92
800	0.09	673 a	52 a	92
1,000	0.08	820 a	80 a	90
Control (300 liters water)	0.00	908 a	694 b	24

^aTo induce buildup of BPH population, the field was sprayed six times with 25 g a.i. cypermethrin/ha at 10-day intervals.

^bIn a column, any means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.